

Self-configuring metro-access network with OpenXR Pluggables and filter-less OADMs

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Abstract: We present a Proof-of-Concept (PoC) of a metro-access optical network that uses automatic reconfigurable OpenXR Pluggables and Filter-less Optical Add-Drop Multiplexers (OADMs) over a chain of access nodes connected to two metro nodes in a horseshoe topology. Each OADM consists of optical splitters and Semiconductor Optical Amplifiers (SOAs), whose gains are individually managed by an open-source network controller. Two sets of XR Pluggables were stacked operating both in a Point-to-Point (P2P) and Point-to-MultiPoint (P2MP) configurations. We carried out physical layer experiments and tested Control Plane aspects to assess the performance of the proposed network.

1. Introduction

A pervasive 5G/6G infrastructure is emerging as the key enabler to support a wide spectrum of services and applications that fulfill the goals of Industry 4.0. A defining feature is the convergence of wireline and wireless networks to address challenges like scalability in terms of the offered capacity, support for low-latency services, low cost, and power consumption efficiency. In this context, an architectural approach that is increasingly gaining attention is the *optical continuum* under which dissimilar transportation modes and bandwidth granularities are transparently connected over different network segments. For the time being, architectural innovations like the optical continuum will evolve alongside legacy approaches postulating line termination and data processing at the interface between network segment boundaries. The access and metro network segments are the focus of the work in this paper.

Regarding the metro network, the advantages of low-cost, filter-less solutions are now well-established [1], [2], to support the increasing (and different in nature) levels of fixed and mobile internet traffic. Specifically, transmission systems in the metro segment are being upgraded from 10G per wavelength to 100G and 400G through various technologies (e.g. OIF ZR [3]). Moreover, the operators are seeking architectural solutions to limit or remove Reconfigurable/Optical Add-Drop Multiplexers (R/OADMs) as these are considered too costly.

Access network technologies are currently dominated by Time-Division Multiplexing Passive Optical Network (TDM-PON) systems for residential applications (e.g. GPON and XGS-PON) and Point-to-Point (P2P) systems for mobile applications.

3GPP defined 5G NR [4] Radio Access Network (RAN) architecture with functional splits between Radio Unit, Distributed Unit and Central Unit (RU, DU and CU) to better facilitate virtualization with flexible assignment of computing resources [5], i.e. vRAN. Additionally, it allows more efficient use resources as CU can support several DUs, and each DU can support several RUs. However, the new disaggregated RAN architecture brings about a tradeoff between RU complexity and the transport capacity as well as latency, i.e. the high-layer split option (F1 Interface), where the RU/DU are implemented on-site and requires service level

transportation capacity with relaxed latency requirements, and low-layer split option (Fx Interface) with less functionality at the cell site but requiring significant high transport capacity and, more importantly, very stringent latency and jitter requirements. The main advantage of the low-layer split option, aside from the centralization of the DU functionality (C-RAN), is that it maximizes the RF bandwidth utilization, and eases the user equipment hand-over between two adjacent cells.

One of the main aspects of a metro-access network is the sharing of the access infrastructure by residential and mobile users whose traffic is transported over the same Optical Distribution Network (ODN). While some of the traffic (mostly residential) will be terminated at the access node, other traffic such as mobile can optically bypass the access node (optical continuum) and be terminated in the metro node at the DU (Front-Haul) or CU (Mid-Haul) depending on the RAN architectural choices made by the operator.

To the best of the authors' knowledge, no self-configuring metro-access network has been proposed and experimentally validated to date. The most relevant study, also proposed by our team, introduced a SOA-based OADM architecture for digital subcarrier multiplexing (DSCM) [6], where we demonstrated physical-layer performance. However, this work did not include a control-layer demonstration and, therefore, did not achieve self-configuration.

Reference [7] introduced and discussed the feasibility of automatic multi-layer, multi-domain transport networks concept but without experimental validation. The main challenges of self-configuration lie not only in integrating multiple network layers and unifying interfaces but also in incorporating the latest technologies to achieve a synergistic effect, where the combined system outperforms the sum of its individual components. The initial planned Proof-of-Concept (PoC) was to simultaneously set up residential and mobile connections using Infinera's OpenXR optics [8] and filter-less OADM that can be easily integrated into Photonic Integrated Circuits (PICs) using Semiconductor Optical Amplifiers (SOAs) and passive optical splitters/combiners. The End-to-End (E2E) network would be centrally controlled, including the ITU-T XGS-PON systems by Ciena used for residential applications. Both the XGS-PON and Infinera's OpenXR optics can be used over Point-to-MultiPoint (P2MP) fiber infrastructure, which is key to reducing costs while still supporting the high bandwidth demand [9]. Coherent P2MP DSCM-based technology brings about efficiencies in the form of reduction in the number of transceivers thanks to optical aggregation [10], which has a direct impact on the power consumption since it is a major factor in the energy consumption at the traffic aggregation nodes [11], [12]. Moreover, DSCM-based transmission schemes exhibit operational flexibility through the reconfigurability of bandwidth resources according to the traffic conditions of the network, opening the potential for scaling down the operating conditions of the transceivers when the demand decreases, thus allowing for energy savings with respect to full-capacity operation [13]. The optical element in the metro node that can maximize the advantages of the P2MP technologies and enable the optical continuum is an advanced filter-less component as an OADM. Through a sub-equipped testbed, we showcase the end-to-end operation with the aid of a novel SDN-enabled Control Plane. Therefore, it is this combination of flexibility and cost-efficiency what makes a filter-less architecture attractive for applications beyond 5G over a consolidated Metro-Access network.

The remainder of the article is structured as follows. In Section 2 we present an overview of the "optical continuum" concept, and we elaborate on the architectural objectives. In Section 3, we introduce the filter-less OADM and the characteristics of the variable gain SOAs to control traffic connectivity across the metro and access segments. Section 4 describes the experimental setup, which included two pairs of OpenXR pluggable transceivers that were operated at different wavelengths: one for residential traffic configured as a P2MP connection that is terminated at the access node and one for mobile traffic configured as a P2P connection, which optically bypasses the access node. In Section 5, we briefly present the hierarchical

Control Plane developed in the B5G-OPEN project¹ for dynamic service provisioning, B5G-ONP that being the main orchestrator, manages the XGS-PON and sets the SOA gain configurations in the OADMs. Although the OpenXR pluggables control should be under B5G-ONP umbrella, the project had no control over the development of the pluggables and thus the PoC was supported by Infinera’s Intelligent Pluggable Manager (IPM) instead. Section 6 reports the main experimental results where we demonstrated error-free transmission for both P2MP and P2P connections using OpenXR Pluggables and SOAs adjusted to maintain connection quality. The results showed that the system could handle up to 14 dB attenuation by adjusting the SOA gains. Last, Section 7 discusses the next work and draws on the conclusions.

2. Optical continuum concept in a Metro-Access integration

An overview of the end-to-end (E2E) architecture is shown on Fig.1. Residential users are interfaced to two separate ODNs (using single fiber working systems) having as a termination point in the Access Central Offices (Access COs) while a Macro-cell is interfaced to the ODN at the right-hand side of Fig.1 bypassing the Access CO, through an optical circulator as adaptation between single (Access) and double (Metro) fiber working network segments, and through the optical filter-less OADM. The mobile traffic is terminated at the Metro CO where the CU is hosted. By means of this PoC we are able to showcase key features addressed during the B5G-OPEN project [14]: (a) mobile traffic is connected between the cell site and the metro node, optically bypassing the access CO in an optical continuum [15], (b) both Fiber-to-the-Premises (FTTP) (residential) and RAN (mobile) use the same fiber infrastructure (single fiber working) in the integrated access network, (c) the access node optical bypass leads to traffic consolidation in the Metro part, (d) the necessary condition to implement the optical continuum is the introduction of a multi-band technology: mobile traffic uses the C-Band to reach a longer transmission distance, while the residential traffic through the XGS-PON uses the O-Band from ONUs to OLT, and the upper end of the C-Band in the downstream towards the ONU in a Multi-Band operation, (e) the central controller B5G-ONP manages the service traffic E2E and the network configuration for all types of traffic.

Figure 1. PoC diagram. 5G NC: Next-Generation Core; ONU: Optical Network Unit; RU: Radio Unit; DU: Distribution Unit; CU: Central Unit. Control plane shown in Blue and Access fibers in Yellow.

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The optical bypass of the access node brings about substantial reductions in power consumption mainly due to a significant metro node consolidation [16], [17], [18] and bypass of packet routers in the access nodes. Consolidation and absence of packet processing until the node where the CU functionality is implemented leads to latency reduction.

The transparent and cost-effective metro network is showcased by emulating BT's network as a horseshoe topology illustrated in Fig. 2 [14], which consists of a chain of N access nodes interconnecting two metro nodes. The access nodes host the OLTs that terminate e.g. residential traffic.

Figure 2. Metro network in a horseshoe topology.

While the main traffic is connected to Metro Central Office (CO) #1, the Metro CO #2 is used for resilience. Traffic originating from the remote access points (e.g. mobile sites or premises) is collected, groomed, and forwarded towards the Metro CO #1 (upstream) bypassing access nodes in-between. Traffic transmitted from the metro node towards the access points via the access nodes (downstream) where it will be demultiplexed to find its final destination. The architecture and design of access nodes is crucial to realize next generation metro-access networks and to support the increasing traffic demand, while minimizing both Capital Expenditure (CapEx) and Operation Expenditure (OpEx) in terms of power consumption [9].

3. Filter-less OADM

A key element in the PoC is the filter-less OADM [19]. It uses discrete variable gain SOAs and passive optical splitters as depicted in Fig. 3. The working metro node, or previous OADM in the chain, is connected to the west port, while the east port is connected to the next OADM in the chain or the protection metro node. Working local traffic at wavelength 1 (Leaf node), is dropped and collected at the south port of the OADM. Note that Fig. 3 does not show traffic protection that would require an additional set of optical transceivers at a different wavelength from an additional Leaf node.

Figure 3. Filter-less OADM configuration. US: upstream, DS: downstream, LT1: optical 90:10 splitter/tap, LT2: optical splitter.

The filter-less OADM was designed to be used with Infinera's OpenXR Pluggables targeting deployment within the metro segment and extending through to the access segment

for mobile applications. OpenXR pluggables are coherent transceivers capable of transmitting in P2P and P2MP configuration [20]. In both, transmission from lower-speed devices (e.g. 100G) to higher-speed ones (e.g. 400G), and vice versa, is possible. The key digital communication technique this technology uses is DSCM, which creates lower-speed 25G channels in the digital domain at the transmitter that can be individually detected at the coherent receiver, using 16 Quadrature Amplitude Modulation (16QAM) and dual polarization.

The “downstream” (DS) connections, i.e. from the XR transmitter at the Hub in the metro node to the XR receivers at the Leaf nodes within the access node or the mobile cell sites, enters the OADM on the west port (Fig. 3). Inside the OADM, the traffic goes through SOA-1, which is set with gain G_1 , before being split at the LT1 (90:10 optical tap) into the south port for the local traffic and pass-through out to the east port (bottom right in Fig. 3) towards the next OADM. This latter traffic may be further amplified by an optional SOA-2 set with gain G_2 . Depending on the fiber length in the next span, SOA-2 may not be included in the design.

The “upstream” (US) traffic connection, i.e. from the XR transmitters at the Leaf nodes to the XR receiver at the Hub, enters the OADM at the east port (top right in Fig. 3) where it goes through SOA-3, with gain G_3 . SOA-3 is used to both compensate for the transmission losses of the previous fiber span, and to equalize with the traffic being added locally at the south port. The in-line and local traffic are combined at the optical combiner LT2, which is an optical splitter for local/in-line traffic. The total traffic is sent to the east output port (top left in Fig. 3) after being amplified through the SOA-4, with gain G_4 to overcome the transmission losses in the next fiber span.

Figure 4. SOA evaluation boards and splitters used in the PoC for the OADMs.

In this experiment, we used two development boards with four SOAs each (Fig. 4), using six of them to build two full OADMs. The SOAs were codenamed SOA.x.y, (SOA “x” inside board “y”, with $x = 1..4$ and $y = 1..2$). The SOAs were characterized in terms of Gain and Noise figure. An exemplary of the characterization is shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5. Characterization of SOA.4.1 as an example

This SOA characterization is necessary for the Control Agent to set up the individual gains based on the instructions from the Central Controller. In addition, the Agent uses the Noise Figure to calculate the feasibility of new connections via OSNR degradation.

4. Proof-of-Concept setup

We used four OpenXR Pluggables for the PoC, with two OpenXR systems at different wavelengths, one of them configured as a P2MP service for residential traffic, and the other as a P2P service for mobile traffic. The setup is illustrated in Fig. 6.

Figure 6. Setup of the Filter-less Metro-Access Network PoC. NDU: Network Distribution Unit. Control Plane in Blue, Access fibers in Yellow, and auxiliary elements for the experiments in Green.

The inset picture on the top left of Fig. 6 shows the router Nokia 7750 SR1 hosting the XR Hub 1 QSFP-DD that was connected to the XR Leaf 1 in a P2MP configuration using 16 digital subcarriers with a total capacity of 400 Gb/s. The XR Hub 2 QSFP-DD hosted by an Infinera NDUs was connected to the XR Leaf 2, hosted by another NDU, configured as a P2P connection using 4 digital subcarriers.

The fiber distance between the metro node and the first OADM at the first access node was 10 km, and the fiber distance between the first OADM in the first access node and the second OADM in the second access node was 50 km. The local traffic in the first access node was transported over two Ciena XGS-PONs systems (cf. OLT & ONUs picture insets in Fig. 6).

The mobile traffic was connected to the East port of OADM-2. Due to the limited number of available XR Pluggables, we connected the mobile traffic to the fiber infrastructure of the first access node by converting between dual and single fiber working so the mobile traffic could be transported over the access network infrastructure, coexisting with the XGS-PON in the same fiber.

We inserted Variable Optical Attenuators (VOAs) to run tests in the physical layer and two Optical Spectrum Analyzers (OSAs) to display the spectrum content in the metro network. While the XR Pluggables were locally managed, both the PON systems and the SOA gains in the OADMs were remotely controlled to set their gains depending on optical losses and number of active digital subcarriers.

5. Control, Orchestration and Management

This PoC leverages a Control Plane that enables the dynamic provisioning of services [21]. It is based on the control, management and orchestration platform developed in the B5G-OPEN project that has been partially validated in [22], [23] and more recently in [24], [25].

5.1 Functional architecture and components

The Control Plane architecture relies on a hierarchical arrangement of controllers (Fig. 7). In the following, we detail the basic elements of its architecture and roles.

Figure 7. Functional description of each component in the Control Plane architecture.

On top of the Control Plane sits the B5G-ONP, which is the main orchestrator and network planner. It allows in-operation network planning and overall service deployment. It processes the service requests and delegates the configuration to underlying subsystems based on the specific workflow and use case. In this PoC, based on the architecture, B5G-ONP delegates the configuration of the OpenXR Pluggables to the IPM, the configuration of the XGS-PON and the Optical Line System (OLS) encompassing multiple OADMs to their respective controllers. The B5G-ONP consists of three main modules: (i) the provisioning and discovery module, which is intended to manage the provisioning and termination of different operator-level services. Such functions are accessed via an Application Programming Interface (API); (ii) the dimensioning and analysis module hosts different algorithmic resources, that realize the resource allocation decisions, in different use cases, covering both offline network dimensioning, and online resource allocations; and (iii) the Optical Path Computation Engine (OPCE) is specifically developed to be able to determine the best path for the optical connections based on the available resources interacting with the Transport API (TAPI) Optical Network Orchestrator (OADM Controller), in order to act as an OPCE node, to which the TAPI Optical Network Orchestrator (OADM Controller) can delegate the optical path computations.

In Fig. 8, we show the B5G-ONP Graphical User Interface with a network that was used in the Control Plane validations. This network provides us with an example of how to integrate with the other controllers and rather than the whole final PoC setup it shows the OpenXR system pluggable connectivity through the Filter-less OADMs. The two XR Hub nodes are hosted by the Nokia 7750 SR1 and the Leaf nodes are hosted by the different Infinera NDUs. The filter-less OADMs are represented by the “node_1”, “node_2”, and “node_3” in the graph. As reported in [25] the OADM controller and the PON Manager are integrated in the same network design and it can be seen on the left hand-side of Fig. 8 as “Domain 1” and “Access” respectively.

Figure 8. Graphical User Interface of B5G-ONP with an example Control Plane architecture.

The IPM controller is responsible for configuring the OpenXR pluggables offering a REST interface. Clients of the IPM may define OpenXR networks, with their hub and leaf nodes and the specific properties of the DSCM signal (e.g., constellation and modulation format). The configuration of the pluggable transceivers is then performed in different stages and can either be pre-configured or in coordination with the OADM line system.

The B5G-ONP supports the control of access network segments in addition to the control and orchestration of packet and optical network segments. The PON infrastructure of the PoC is realized using Ciena XGS-PON OLT pluggable transceivers (formerly Tibit) and a couple of ONUs per OLT. The OLT is interfaced directly to a Layer 2 switch (used as a host and also as a port disaggregation) and connected to the ONUs by means of a P2MP ODN. Integration with the B5G-ONP platform is made feasible at three different levels down to the PON agent.

Figure 9. Graphical User Interface of the FlexOpt optical SDN Controller, responsible for configuring the SOAs upon service provisioning

The OADM controller is implemented in terms of the CTTC FlexOpt SDN Controller and is responsible for configuring, upon request, the SOA gains on a per-node abstraction and aggregation. A specific device model has been developed to abstract the individual OADMs admitting the configuration of the individual SOAs with exported parameters such as the applicable Gain and Noise Figure. The OADM controller exports a north bound interface that relies on the Linux foundation TAPI [26] models and interfaces. We have extended the provisioning model to support P2MP media channels (light-trees) for specific bus-like/filter-less scenarios like the ones shown in Fig. 9, including the applicable configuration at each node/SOA.

An SDN agent has been designed and implemented to enable the remote configuration and control of the SOAs in each OADMs. This agent has been developed in Python with a REST interface on port 5000 of each device. The agent maps the REST interface POST operations into SOA configurations. The Filter-less OADM controller was designed using an HTTP agent. To enhance the robustness of the SOA-based OADM, we utilized a poly53 polynomial model to fit the characterized SOA data, storing the coefficients of the function for each SOA within the agent. As illustrated in the diagram, when the control layer sends a request to the agent with input parameters of -5 dBm input power and a desired gain of 10 dB, the model calculates the required SOA drive current to be 41 mA (Fig. 10).

Figure 10. Illustration of the methodology by which the OADM agent employed the SOA characterization to determine the requisite current level to achieve the desired Gain.

6. Experimental measurements and results

Fig. 11 shows a diagram of the connectivity of the OpenXR systems used in the PoC with two pluggables as Hub nodes (in the metro node) each connected with a Leaf node at two access nodes. The work in [16] analyzed, through modeling and simulations, the scalability and link margin of a chain of Filter-less OADM based on the SOA characterization data as shown in Fig. 5 and simulated the scalability and link margin in detail. Here, we show only the connectivity of the XR Pluggables by splitting the downstream (Fig. 11(a)) and upstream (Fig. 11(b)) directions. Four Ethernet traffic flows (2×5 GbE and 2×1GbE) were configured between the Metro node and residential users over the Metro P2MP OpenXR system (XH-1 – XL-1) and each XGS-PON (not shown), which were running error-free throughout the experiments. As mentioned earlier, the XR system configured as P2P (XH-2 – LH-2), and carrying an Ethernet 100 GbE traffic flow, coexisted in the same 5 km access fiber as one of the PON systems. There was an adaptation between Metro and Access segments with a conversion between dual fiber working and single fiber working using an optical circulator. The traffic of the XR system configured as P2MP was also present in the access fiber connecting to the

Mobile site because the OADMs were splitter based. Two VOAs were inserted to carry out basic experiments at the physical layer.

Figure 11. Diagrams showing the OpenXR systems connectivity split in (a) downstream and (b) upstream.

As this block diagram considers only the data-plane, we do not show the SDN controllers. However, from an architectural and control plane workflow perspective, the B5G-ONP should compute the optimal SOA configuration based on retrieved physical layer impairments and additional configuration. Once this has been computed, the per SOA configuration is encoded using JSON format and passed to the FlexOpt SDN controller as a T-API extension during the service provisioning process, as an attribute of the requested connectivity service. The FlexOpt SDN controller then proceeds to send this configuration on a per node basis using a REST based interface to each of the Network elements. Reconfiguration can be applied upon detection of events – by monitoring or polling (not implemented)– and sending a service modification to the optical controller. In our context, the SOA gains were pre-computed and provided to the planner entity, which forwards it to the SDN controller.

However, the PoC did not include the algorithm to calculate the configuration of the SOA gains to establish or re-establish the connections after any change in the setup. Therefore, the experiment procedure was to manually change the value of the VOAs and use the OADM agents to adapt, if necessary, the gain of the SOAs to re-establish the error-free connection. The starting network configuration (or baseline configuration) was error free.

Fig. 12 shows the results in the downstream direction (Fig. 11(a)) for the XR system configured as a P2MP connection between the XR-Hub 1 and XR Leaf 1.

Figure 12. Downstream pre-FEC results as VOA value increased (event) and SOA.1.1 Gain re-configured to re-establish error-free connection at the Open XR Leaf 1.

Each event (x-axis) represents a variation in the value of the VOA (manual), which degraded the pre-Forward Error Correction (pre-FEC). The effect of the VOA is to increase the span losses and to create a power imbalance between in-line and added subcarriers, which is a typical scenario in a P2MP metro-aggregation architecture, such as the one here investigated. When pre-FEC reached the FEC threshold, the connection started displaying errors, and consequently the gain of the SOA.1.1 was increased (manually using the OADM agent controller) to compensate for the higher attenuation, so that an error-free connection could be re-established. The same procedure was used for the graphs shown in the next three figures.

We can observe from Fig. 12 that we were able to increase the VOA to 14 dB and maintain an error-free connection, thanks to a gain of 14 dB provided by SOA1.1. Incidentally, this represents also an improvement of 4 dB in tolerance to power imbalance with respect to [27], where the OpenXR transceiver could operate error-free till 10 dB of power imbalance.

The basic nature of the experiments meant that despite the Control Plane being fully implemented it was not possible to perform control plane related measurements like restoration time.

Figure 13. Downstream Pre-FEC results as VOA value increased (event) and SOA.1.1 Gain re-configured to re-establish error-free connection at the OpenXR Leaf 2

Fig. 13 shows the results for the P2P connection error-free for a VOA value of 14 dB and a SOA gain of 14 dB. It must be noted that both sets of measurements (Figs. 12 and 13) were taken simultaneously and they are shown in two different graphs for clarity only. The change of the VOA value affects both XR systems simultaneously and it is reasonable that, as both Leaf nodes have been configured to receive four digital subcarriers using 16QAM and same pre-FEC threshold, both modules can cope with an attenuation up to 14 dB. Obviously with this experiment we are only emulating an added insertion loss caused by e.g., connectors, or a kink in the fiber cable, or difference distances of the several leaf nodes connected to the same network. The other main factor of degradation is the OSNR (analyzed in [19]), which is directly linked to the pre-FEC and only depends on the number of traversed SOAs, being the same in all cases. We have not analyzed other potential effects of increasing the transmission distance, although non-linear effects should not degrade the signal since launched optical powers per connection have always been kept around or below 0 dBm (of all DSCs).

We have performed the same type of experiments in the upstream direction but inserting the VOA before OADM-2 as shown in Fig. 11(b).

Figure 14. Upstream pre-FEC results as VOA value increased (event) and SOA.2.2 Gain re-configured to re-establish error-free connection at the OpenXR Hub 1

The location of the VOA does not impact on the P2MP system and thus we were not expecting a significant variation on its measured BER, which is confirmed by the results shown in Fig. 14. However, even though the transmission is always error-free, there is a change in the BER. This is due to two main reasons, the change in ASE noise generated at the SOA.2.2 when varying its gain, and the change in optical transmitted power at the XR Leaf 1, which automatically adapts when the OpenXR Pluggables are configured as P2MP connections, to equalize with the in-line transmission at the insertion point of the OADM. This control mechanism, inherent in the OpenXR Pluggable when configured as a P2MP system, works with the SOA-3 of the filter-less OADM as shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 15. Upstream pre-FEC results as VOA value increased (event) and SOA.2.2 Gain re-configured to re-establish error-free connection at the OpenXR Hub 2

Fig. 15 shows the impact of changing the VOA value on the P2P XR system between the XR Leaf 2 and XR Hub 2. It shows that by increasing the SOA's gain up to 18 dB (the maximum we were able to configure), the P2P system can cope with a VOA value of 12 dB. However, the maximum value of the VOA the system runs error-free is 14 dB, which can be achieved when the SOA gain is configured with a 14 dB gain. Without verification, we can presume this is due to the ASE noise generated by the SOA.

Fig. 16 shows the "downstream" spectra in the Metro segment, for a baseline configuration, which includes a VOA value of 0 dB and SOA1.1 gain of 6 dB. It shows the P2MP connection with 16 DSC located at a central wavelength of 1544.53 nm (i.e., 194.1 THz), and the P2MP connections with 4 DSC located at a central wavelength of 1534.73 nm (i.e. 194.2 THz). The first graph shows the spectrum of the launched optical signal at the multiplexing point in the Metro node. The second graph (orange color) shows the dropped optical spectrum at the south port of the first OADM after travelling 11 km of fiber, traversing SOA1.1 and through the 10 dB loss of the optical LT1 splitter/tap. The curve in green shows the spectrum at the east output port of the second and last OADM, where it has gone through the SOA2.1. The spectrum in the access fiber on the right hand-side of Fig.6 is not shown, which would include the XGS-PON, although it is easy to imagine as it uses the downstream band 1575-1580nm, i.e. more than 30 nm away from the closest XR system and easily rejected by XR coherent receiver while the XR downstream signals are rejected at the ONU receivers by the optical blocking filters.

Figure 16. Downstream Optical Spectra showing P2P connection on the left and P2MP connection on the right

Fig. 17 shows the “upstream” spectra for a baseline configuration, which includes a VOA value of 0 dB and SOA2.2 gain of 2 dB. It shows the P2MP connection with 4 DSCs transmitted by Leaf node 1, located at a central wavelength of 1544.53 nm (i.e., 194.1 THz), and the P2P connections with 4 DSCs transmitted by Leaf node 2, located at a central wavelength of 1534.73 nm (i.e. 194.2 THz). The graph in green shows the spectra at the west output port of OADM-1 and the second graph in purple shows the optical spectrum after 11 km fiber, at the demultiplexing fiber point before the XR Hub receivers. As in the previous Fig. 16, the XGS-PON spectrum is not shown. The upstream channel uses 1260-1280nm band, i.e. more than 250 nm away from the closest XR signals, which is easily filtered out at the XR coherent receiver while the XR upstream signals are rejected by the diplexer filter at the XGS-PON OLT Transceiver.

Figure 17. Upstream Optical Spectra showing P2P connection on the left and P2MP connection on the right.

7. Discussion, conclusions and future work

Next-generation metro-aggregation and access networks will necessitate high-capacity transmission capabilities to accommodate the ever-increasing traffic in network segments such as metro and access. Furthermore, operators require simplified, flexible and scalable solutions that can coexist with legacy technologies and support a pay-as-you-grow strategy, thereby enabling the deployment of resources as required. Within this framework, an automated packet optical metro-access network architecture with a horseshoe topology (characteristic in some

major European operators) was demonstrated with a PoC, integrating both control and data planes.

As part of our Metro-Access Network PoC, we carried out validation (through some basic experiments) of novel coherent transceivers capable of functioning in both point-to-point and point-to-multipoint configurations. Both configurations facilitate communication between two transceivers operating at different data-rates, thereby augmenting scalability through the incremental addition (WDM stacking) of pluggables as required. Additionally, we integrated the use of a Filter-less Optical Add-Drop Multiplexer with the Control Plane developed as part of the EU-funded B5G-OPEN project. All components of the network architecture exhibited in this article demonstrated high-capacity transmission and effective control management over P2MP fiber infrastructure. Additionally, the transceivers' capability to manage imbalanced power levels resultant from digital subcarriers received from various leaf nodes at disparate distances was validated, alongside the efficacy of the developed Control Plane. However, the PoC did not implement the model to calculate SOA gains to offset losses occurring in both the upstream and downstream directions and neither did we implement polling or monitoring tools to detect failure events, which will be part of future work.

Ultimately, the proposed architecture possesses the potential for deployment to accommodate increasing traffic demands by utilizing existing PON systems while facilitating coexistence with legacy traffic. The PoC demonstrated the potential for the network concept and the experiments showed that when the span losses change due to, e.g., protection switching, the network can automatically readjust its configuration to recover error-free connections.

Putting together an automated packet optical metro-access network architecture with both the control and data planes is a complex endeavor, and the number of tests and experiments that can be carried out are potentially limitless. Although a limited set of results and test scenarios have been presented, it shows the concept is going in the right direction. Future work is expected to further validate this network concept and carry out further tests and experiments.

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